

Resolution and Sidelobe Structure Analysis for RF Tomography

Jason T. Parker, Linda J. Moore

Sensors Directorate

US Air Force Research Laboratory

Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433

Email: {jason.parker,linda.moore2}@wpafb.af.mil

Lee C. Potter

The Ohio State University

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Columbus, OH 43210

Email: potter@ece.osu.edu

Abstract—Radio frequency (RF) tomography utilizes a network of spatially diverse sensors to trade geometric diversity for bandwidth, permitting images to be formed with narrowband waveforms. Such a constellation of sensors produces a sparsely and irregularly spaced set of Fourier space samples, complicating the definition and analysis of resolution for these systems. We present an analysis of resolution for RF tomography based on the Cramér Rao Bound (CRB) for estimation of target position and velocity. This approach allows the resolution for a given sensor configuration to be determined with minimal computational cost, thus providing a useful design tool for sensor placement and frequency selection for RF tomography. We also explore the impact of Fourier space “filling” with bistatic geometries on sidelobe structure of the ambiguity function. Several simulation results are presented to validate the resolution calculations from the CRB and to illustrate the importance of sensor placement for RF tomographic imaging.

I. INTRODUCTION

A monostatic radar system can utilize wide bandwidth pulses to form high resolution images over relatively small, densely-sampled synthetic apertures. However, such a system requires significant bandwidth to operate, offers a single viewing direction into urban canyons, and represents a single point of failure. To cope with shrinking available spectrum and provide redundancy both in look directions and viewpoints, RF tomography replaces this single monostatic asset with a network or constellation of narrowband radars operating cooperatively to form multistatic images. Such a system could use inexpensive sensors with minimal analog-to-digital converter (ADC) requirements, provide multiple viewpoints into urban canyons and other obscured environments, and offer graceful performance degradation under sensor attrition.

A variety of technical challenges must be addressed to realize such a system. In this paper we study the resolution and sidelobe structure that can be obtained using widely spaced, narrowband sensors. We shall assume that targets scatter isotropically. The overriding goal of this effort is to obtain a fast method for determining the desirability of a sensor constellation without requiring numerically intensive calculation of the ambiguity function, or point spread function (PSF) in the imaging case. This analysis will form the basis of efforts to optimize sensor placement and frequency selection for an RF tomographic sensor constellation in future work.

Several authors have considered similar problems. First, Cheney and Borden derive very general expressions for the ambiguity function of a multistatic radar configuration [1] that can be used to numerically compute resolution and sidelobe structure. In [2], the authors derive the CRB for estimating 3D position and complex amplitude of a group of scatterers from a non-linear monostatic flight path. The analysis is used to justify sinusoidal variation in elevation and range of the radar platform flight path to form a 3D synthetic aperture that can be used to eliminate layover ambiguities in formed SAR imagery. A detailed study of sparse radar array resolution is undertaken in [3]. The authors focus on a single transmitter with multiple receivers in a quasi-monostatic space-based radar scenario. Since they focus on stationary targets restricted to a plane, they are able to project all of the data samples onto two “eigen-sensors” that allow them to easily calculate resolution and sidelobe structure for their geometries. They obtain excellent prediction of the ambiguity function volume using both the CRB and a non-statistical approach. Indeed, our approach is closely related to this work.

Several attempts have also been made to optimize the resolution obtained using distributed sensors. In [4], Bradaric et al. explore choosing waveforms, sensor positions, and weighting of bistatic pairs to shape the ambiguity function of a multistatic constellation. Noncoherent combination of distributed radar data is explored in [5] from a detection point of view. Fang, Cheney, and Roecker [6] explore the computation of weights over a sparsely populated aperture similar to the one considered here to improve the point spread function of a filtered backprojection imaging approach. Fogle and Rigling [7] assume a linear mapping from target position to collected bistatic measurements and derive the CRB for target position estimation. By assuming linearity, they are able to derive a closed form expression for the gradient of the CRB matrix determinant and use this result to find locally optimal sensor geometries. They extend these results for the near-field case with sensors constrained to a known surface. In [8] and [9], point spread functions for 3D static scenes given non-linear monostatic flight paths were numerically computed. Finally, the authors’ own previous work [10] explored resolution issues for monostatic circular SAR using a very similar approach to the one pursued in this work.

Here, we will attempt to predict the resolution for a given sensor geometry using a result derived based on the CRB for the estimation error of a single target's position. We will adopt the common abuse of terminology and use "resolution" to refer to the volume (or area in the 2D case) of the central peak of the ambiguity function. The CRB provides a lower bound on the error variance of any unbiased estimator. Geometrically, the CRB uses the curvature of the ambiguity function at its peak to characterize the precision with which a location can be estimated in noise. As seen below, the CRB approach is able to predict the ambiguity function's main lobe volume very accurately, just as in [3]. Furthermore, this CRB calculation requires only a fraction of the computation required to compute the actual ambiguity function. We will extend this analysis to computing resolution in position/velocity phase space for moving targets.

The paper is organized as follows. We develop our far-field signal model in Section II and review the derivation of the CRB for stationary target position in Section III. The extension of the CRB analysis to moving targets is given in Section IV. Finally, a series of numerical simulations verifying the accuracy of the resolution predictions and exploring the impact of bistatic k-space filling on sidelobe structure are presented in Section V.

II. FAR FIELD SIGNAL MODEL

Consider a set of N data points indexed by n collected at frequencies $\omega_n = 2\pi f_n$ from transmit and receive positions $t_n, r_n \in \mathbb{R}^3$. For a suitably small scene centered at the point $p \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and by adopting an isotropic point scatterer model, we can characterize the data in terms of k-space sampling locations given by

$$\begin{aligned} k_n &= \frac{2\pi f_n}{c} (\widehat{t_n - p} + \widehat{r_n - p}) \\ &= \frac{4\pi f_n}{c} \cos\left(\frac{\beta_n}{2}\right) [\cos\theta_n \cos\phi_n, \sin\theta_n \cos\phi_n, \sin\phi_n]^T, \end{aligned}$$

where c is the speed of light, \hat{x} is a unit vector, and β_n, θ_n , and ϕ_n represent the bistatic angle and the azimuth/elevation of the bistatic bisector for measurement n .

We can then express the phase history for a point scatterer at displacement from p given by $r = [x, y, z] \in \mathbb{R}^3$ as $D \in \mathbb{C}^N$ where the n^{th} entry of D is

$$\begin{aligned} d_n &= Ae^{j\psi} e^{jk_n \cdot r} + \varepsilon_n \\ &= s_n(\Theta) + \varepsilon_n. \end{aligned}$$

Here we have denoted the complex amplitude of the point scatterer as $Ae^{j\psi}$, and the additive noise as $\varepsilon_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$. We use $s_n(\Theta)$ to denote the n^{th} element of the noise-free "steering vector" $S(\Theta)$ parameterized by the real vector $\Theta = [A, \psi, x, y, z]^T$.

III. CRB FOR POSITION ESTIMATION

Here we compute the CRB for estimating Θ from the phase history D . We first note that $p(D|\Theta) \sim \mathcal{CN}(S(\Theta), \sigma^2 I)$. The

entries of Fisher's Information Matrix (FIM) are then given by [11]

$$I(\Theta)_{ij} = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\partial S^H(\Theta)}{\partial \Theta_i} \frac{\partial S(\Theta)}{\partial \Theta_j} \right\}. \quad (1)$$

Define the sample covariance matrix of the k-space sampling locations by C given as

$$C = R - \mu\mu^T,$$

where the centroid of the k-space sampling locations and the sample correlation matrix R are given by

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N k_n \quad (2)$$

$$R = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N k_n k_n^T. \quad (3)$$

A straightforward exercise demonstrates that the FIM can be expressed as

$$I_r(\Theta) = \frac{2NA^2}{\sigma^2} \begin{bmatrix} A^{-2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \mu_x & \mu_y & \mu_z \\ 0 & \mu_x & & & \\ 0 & \mu_y & & R & \\ 0 & \mu_z & & & \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

By partitioning the FIM into blocks, we can compute the CRB submatrix for position accuracy as the inverse of the Schur complement to obtain [12], [13],

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CRB}_r &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2NA^2} \left(R - \begin{bmatrix} 0_3 & \mu \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0_3^T \\ \mu^T \end{bmatrix} \right)^{-1} \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2NA^2} C^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

The CRB represents a quadratic approximation to the central peak of the likelihood function. As such, the error ellipsoid volume can be used as a measure of resolution. The volume in 3D, or the area in 2D, are both proportional to the square root of the determinant of the CRB matrix. The as yet unspecified noise power σ^2 scales the CRB matrix determinant. For simplicity, we will select the noise power so that the CRB results predict the numerically computed volume of various ambiguity functions. Thus, we will adopt

$$V_{xyz}(\alpha) = \alpha \sqrt{\det C^{-1}} \quad (5)$$

as our measure of resolution.

We have replaced the scalar factor in the CRB matrix with a parameter α that we may freely vary. This definition also removes the influence of both the number of k-space samples and the target amplitude from our volume estimate. For each numerical example, we will select α to minimize the mean squared error of our volume predictions based on the CRB versus the numerically calculated ambiguity function volumes. For this specific choice of alpha, the CRB provides a simple and accurate prediction of a numerically computed ambiguity function volume, as is demonstrated in the examples. Since our

goal is to develop a tool for sensor constellation design, this arbitrary scaling of the result is not problematic. Naturally, when using this result for prediction of the performance of a particular estimator, this arbitrary rescaling would be unacceptable.

IV. CRB FOR POSITION AND VELOCITY ESTIMATION

We will now generalize our model to include target velocity. We shall assume that target motion during a given pulse can be neglected¹. To make the model as general as possible, we will simply associate with each data point d_n a slow time parameter given by τ_n . We will augment our parameter vector with the 3D velocity of the target given by $v = [v_x, v_y, v_z]^T$ to obtain $\Theta = [A, \psi, x, y, z, v_x, v_y, v_z]^T$. If we assume that the target velocity is constant during the entire data collection, we obtain the modified phase history data as

$$\begin{aligned} d_n &= Ae^{j\psi} e^{jk_n \cdot (r + \tau_n v)} + \varepsilon_n \\ &= s_n(\Theta) + \varepsilon_n. \end{aligned}$$

A. Arbitrary sensor positions and slow-time sampling

We once again note that $p(D|\Theta) \sim \mathcal{CN}(S(\Theta), \sigma^2 I)$. Application of Equation (1) yields the FIM. We will retain the original definitions for R and C . Define $T = \text{diag}\{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_N\}$ and $K = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n]$. We note that $R = KK^T/N$ and $\mu = K\mathbf{1}_N/N$. Denote the time scaled k-space vectors as $\bar{K} = KT$. Versions of μ and R accounting for the slow time separation of the samples are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mu} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \tau_n k_n = \frac{1}{N} KT\mathbf{1}_N = \frac{1}{N} \bar{K}\mathbf{1}_N \\ \bar{R} &= \frac{1}{N} \bar{K}\bar{K}^T = \frac{1}{N} KT^2K^T. \end{aligned}$$

With these definitions, we can write the FIM as

$$I_{rv}(\Theta) = \frac{2NA^2}{\sigma^2} \begin{bmatrix} A^{-2} & 0 & \mathbf{0}_6^T \\ 0 & 1 & \bar{\mu}^T \\ \mathbf{0}_6 & \bar{\mu} & \bar{R} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where we have defined

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{K} &= \begin{bmatrix} K \\ \bar{K} \end{bmatrix} \\ \tilde{\mu} &= \frac{1}{N} \tilde{K}\mathbf{1}_N \\ \tilde{R} &= \frac{1}{N} \tilde{K}\tilde{K}^T \\ \tilde{C} &= \tilde{R} - \tilde{\mu}\tilde{\mu}^T. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that, as expected, $I_r(\Theta)$ is a submatrix of $I_{rv}(\Theta)$. Once again, we can easily recover the CRB for the six parameters of interest using the Schur complement to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CRB}_{rv} &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2NA^2} \left(\tilde{R} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_6 & \tilde{\mu} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_6^T \\ \tilde{\mu}^T \end{bmatrix} \right)^{-1} \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2NA^2} \tilde{C}^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

¹This standard so called stop-and-hop or move-stop-move approximation is very reasonable for typical pulse-Doppler radar systems [14].

B. Stationary sensors with uniform slow time sampling

Here we consider a special case to gain additional insight into the joint position/velocity CRB expression. Assume that the constellation of sensors is static and that M samples are collected in slow time at a uniform sampling period of $\Delta\tau$, yielding slow times samples $\{0, \Delta\tau, 2\Delta\tau, \dots, (M-1)\Delta\tau\}$ and a total sampling time of $T = (M-1)\Delta\tau$. If we denote the set of N_0 k-space samples at time zero as K_0 , then we can express $K = [K_0 \ K_0 \ \dots \ K_0]^T$. We also notice the following simplifications given $N = MN_0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N k_n = \frac{M}{(MN_0)} \sum_{n=1}^{N_0} k_0 \triangleq \mu_0 \\ \bar{\mu} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \tau_n k_n \\ &= \frac{1}{(MN_0)} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} m\Delta\tau \sum_{n=1}^{N_0} k_0 \\ &= \frac{1}{MN_0} \cdot \frac{\Delta\tau(M-1)M}{2} \cdot N_0\mu_0 \\ &= \frac{\Delta\tau(M-1)}{2} \mu_0 = \frac{T}{2} \mu_0 \\ R &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N k_n k_n^T = \frac{1}{N_0} \sum_{n=1}^{N_0} k_n k_n^T \triangleq R_0 \end{aligned}$$

Notice also that the products involving K and \bar{K} can be simplified as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{N} K\bar{K}^T &= \frac{1}{N} \bar{K}K^T = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\tau_n k_n) k_n^T \\ &= \frac{1}{MN_0} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} m\Delta\tau \sum_{n=1}^{N_0} k_0 k_0^T \\ &= \frac{1}{MN_0} \cdot \frac{\Delta\tau(M-1)M}{2} \cdot N_0 R_0 \\ &= \frac{T}{2} R_0 \\ \frac{1}{N} \bar{K}\bar{K}^T &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\tau_n k_n) (\tau_n k_n)^T \\ &= \frac{1}{MN_0} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \tau_n \tau_n^T \sum_{n=1}^{N_0} k_0 k_0^T \\ &= \frac{1}{MN_0} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} (\Delta\tau)^2 m^2 \sum_{n=1}^{N_0} k_0 k_0^T \\ &= \frac{N_0 R_0}{MN_0} \cdot \frac{(\Delta\tau)^2 (2M-1)(M-1)M}{6} \\ &= \frac{T\Delta\tau(2M-1)}{6} R_0. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting these expressions into (6), we can write the simplified form of the FIM as

$$I_{rv}(\Theta) = \frac{2MN_0A^2}{\sigma^2} \times \begin{bmatrix} A^{-2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \mu_0^T & \frac{T}{2}\mu_0^T & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_0 & R_0 & \frac{T}{2}R_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{T}{2}\mu_0 & \frac{T}{2}R_0 & \frac{T\Delta\tau(2M-1)}{6}R_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In particular, we have obtained the following expressions for $\tilde{\mu}$ and \tilde{R} which may be used to compute the joint CRB for position and velocity estimation,

$$\tilde{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_0 \\ \frac{T}{2}\mu_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\tilde{R} = \begin{bmatrix} R_0 & \frac{T}{2}R_0 \\ \frac{T}{2}R_0 & \frac{T\Delta\tau(2M-1)}{6}R_0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

If either position or velocity is known, then the uncertainty in estimating the other component can be obtained by inverting the appropriate submatrix of $I_{rv}(\Theta)$, as was done in (4) for estimating position with a known (zero) velocity. Exact knowledge of a parameter simplifies the estimation task, and the corresponding CRB will be equal or lower as discussed in [15].

V. EXAMPLES

We present a series of examples using 640 MHz of bandwidth at a center frequency of 10 GHz. These results are not narrowband, but these ranges were selected to allow comparison with monostatic circular SAR. All of the results will compare the 6 dB volume/area of the main peak of the ambiguity function with the estimate computed using (5) or (7). Ambiguity functions are computed via backprojection imaging with uniform weighting of k-space data.

First, we compute the 3D volume of the ambiguity function for a monostatic circular SAR collection covering the entire 360° azimuth range. Figure 1(a) depicts the resulting resolution as a function of the elevation angle selected for the circular flight path. As observed in [10], there is an ideal elevation angle to achieve the best resolution. In addition, the CRB approach almost exactly predicts the main lobe volume after proper selection of α . It is worth emphasizing that the CRB calculation is numerically trivial compared to analytical calculation and volume integration of the true ambiguity function. The computations for the CRB are $\mathcal{O}(N)$ versus $\mathcal{O}(N^2 \log N)$ for fast bistatic backprojection imaging [16] of range/Doppler maps, yielding several orders of magnitude difference in execution times.

We next consider using only 15 sensors placed on the unit circle. For computational convenience, we will restrict our calculations to 2D and report areas rather than volumes. Figure 1(b) depicts the resolution obtained as the azimuth

extent of the sensors is varied. As expected, the resolution is best for the full 360° aperture. It is worth mentioning that the same resolution is obtained with monochromatic returns at the full aperture extent, as the resolution is then dominated by the wavelength rather than the bandwidth. Again, the CRB prediction is nearly exact.

Our next example is meant to highlight the impact of using bistatic returns on the ambiguity function and resolution. Once again, we place 15 sensors in a ring around the target. However, instead of spacing them uniformly, the sensors are placed randomly around the ring. Figure 2 depicts the resulting resolution calculations for 10 random draws of the sensor positions. Two sets of results are provided. The monostatic results utilize only monostatic returns from each of the 15 sensors. The “full” results also include all possible bistatic combinations for the 15 sensors. The CRB resolution prediction is excellent, using the same α for both the monostatic and full cases.

Perhaps surprisingly, the 6 dB volumes for the “full” data sets are larger than the corresponding monostatic-only trials. Since the CRB predictions are normalized to eliminate the gain from using more k-space samples in the full case, they capture this numerical behavior. These results are explained by examining the results of Trial 3 in Fig. 3. The figure depicts the ambiguity function and corresponding k-space support for each of the data sets. The bistatic samples are closer to the origin and individually provide less information about the target location. Thus, the uniform weighting across these samples broadens the mainlobe peak of the ambiguity function. At the same time, the bistatic filling of k-space greatly reduces so called “quasi-grating” lobes [3] or sidelobes in the ambiguity function. A non-uniform quadrature rule for numerical integration of non-uniformly sampled k-space data would provide somewhat superior reconstruction of the ambiguity function [6].

Our penultimate example verifies the joint position/velocity CRB. We again use a set of 15 sensors placed in a ring and vary the azimuth extent covered by the sensors. To make the simulations analytically tractable, we will consider a 4D ambiguity function, 2D position and 2D velocity. As in Section IV-B, we keep the sensors stationary throughout the coherent processing interval (CPI) and utilize a constant pulse repetition frequency (PRF). In Fig. 4, we plot the numerically computed hyper-volume of the ambiguity function mainlobe against the prediction from the square root of the determinant of \tilde{C}^{-1} after appropriate scaling with a constant α . As in the position only examples, the match is excellent.

Finally, we extend the position/velocity example by computing the CRB for several different numbers of pulses, M . In Fig. 5(c), we show the square root of the determinant of \tilde{C}^{-1} for various values of M . In Fig. 5(a,b), we compute the square roots of the determinants of the submatrices associated with position and velocity separately. The curves are normalized so that total transmitted energy is constant. There are several interesting features worth noting on these plots. First, as we would expect, the overall 4D error is lowest for the widest

Fig. 1. (a) Volume of the main lobe of the ambiguity function for a monostatic circular SAR using 360° of azimuth coverage. (b) Restricted to two dimensions for simplicity, the area of the main lobe for a group of 15 fixed sensors using monostatic and bistatic returns spaced uniformly on an arc of increasing azimuth extent.

Fig. 2. Area of the main lobe over several trials as the sensor positions are randomized.

spacing of the sensors. Second, the position accuracy actually goes down as more pulses are used. This is unsurprising under the constant energy constraint, since given our move-stop-move approximation the position can be estimated without an error contribution from velocity using a single pulse. If the CRB for position is computed assuming that the velocity is known, then the various M curves overlap. Finally, the non-monotonic character of the velocity uncertainty plots is a characteristic of the geometry selected. If, for example, the sensors positions are varied so that symmetry about the origin is maintained, this effect disappears.

The key points highlighted by these examples are that the resolution, defined here in terms of the main lobe volume/area, is improved by spreading k -space samples over a wider synthetic aperture. Furthermore, the magnitude and occurrence of sidelobes are reduced by sampling this k -space volume more densely. In addition, it is well known that randomization of these sample locations can improve the sidelobe structure, just as in antenna design [17].

The CRB determinant provides a scalar metric that accurately predicts the resolution of the main lobe peak of the ambiguity function. However, this metric is not informative about the sidelobe structure of the resulting ambiguity function. Nevertheless, this metric may prove useful for fast comparative analysis of sensor placement and frequency selection in RF tomographic sensor constellations.

Fig. 3. Left column: k -space supports for the monostatic (top) and bistatic (bottom) data sets from Trial 3 of Fig. 2. Right column: corresponding numerically computed ambiguity functions showing the top 6 dB. The white boxes illustrate the region identified as containing the main lobe. Due to the uniform aperture weighting used in backprojection imaging, the main lobe is larger using the bistatic data, but the sidelobe structure is significantly suppressed.

Fig. 4. CRB and computed hyper-volume of the main lobe in 4 dimensions, 2D velocity and 2D position. The α parameter was chosen to match the curves in a least-squares sense. Notice that the result is qualitatively very similar to Fig. 1(b), since the same geometries were utilized with a constant PRF.

VI. CONCLUSION

The use of a network of spatially diverse narrowband sensors in RF tomography offers distinct advantages that include the reduction in required operational bandwidth, the availability of multiple viewpoints into obscured environments, and graceful performance degradation under sensor attrition compared to monostatic radar systems. An understanding of the anticipated estimation accuracy of target position and velocity given a network of sensors offers the ability to optimize sensor placement. The CRB provides a lower bound on parameter estimation error variance and is significantly less computationally intensive than numerical calculation of ambiguity function volumes. A generalized expression for the CRB of combined target position/velocity estimation for a network of sensors was derived. From this result, target po-

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5. CRB for (a) position, (b) velocity, and (c) 4D position/velocity for a scenario with 15 sensors spaced deterministically uniformly over various azimuth extents. Each blue curve is for a different number of transmitted pulses, M . The noise power is selected to keep the total transmitted energy constant as the number of pulses is increased. The overall scaling factor α was selected heuristically; the relative amplitudes are the focus of our discussion. The position and velocity bounds are computed by extracting the appropriate submatrices of the CRB matrix and computing the square root of the determinant.

sition and velocity resolutions may be individually extracted. Examples presented demonstrated how the CRB may be used to choose sensor parameters such as elevation angle and azimuth extent in order to achieve desired target parameter estimation accuracy. We also explored the impact of bistatic geometries on the sidelobe structure of the ambiguity function. A major limitation of this approach is the isotropic scattering assumption. Future work may include an analysis of the ambiguity function volume using a stochastic CRB to capture the effects of both anisotropic scattering and obscuration to

improve the utility of this tool for sensor constellation design.

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